

Strategy

Search term groups:

osteoblasts – osteoblast precursors – osteoclasts – osteoclast precursors – bone related words – co-culture related words

Search steps

Include studies mentioning osteoblasts OR osteoblast precursors in combination with bone related words
AND

Include studies mentioning osteoclasts OR osteoclast precursors in combination with bone related words
AND

include studies mentioning co-cultures

PUBMED

Osteoblast

Osteoblasts[[mesh](#)] OR Osteoblast*[tiab] OR Pre-osteoblast*[tiab] OR preosteoblast [tiab] OR osteoprogenitor*[tiab] OR ((Bone forming[tiab] OR osteogenic[tiab]) AND cells[tiab])

Osteoblast progenitor

Mesenchymal stem cells[[mesh](#)] OR Mesenchymal stem[tiab] OR Mesenchymal stromal[tiab] OR Mesenchymal progenitor[tiab] OR bone marrow stem[tiab] OR Bone marrow stromal[tiab] OR MSC*[tiab] OR Multipotent stem[tiab] OR Multipotent stromal[tiab] OR Multi-potent stem[tiab] OR Multi-potent stromal[tiab] OR Stromal cell*[tiab] OR Stromal fraction[tiab] OR Adipose derived stem[tiab] OR Adipose derived stromal[tiab] OR Adipose stem[tiab] OR Adipose stromal[tiab] OR Fat derived stem[tiab] OR Fat derived stromal[tiab] OR MC3T3*[tiab] OR Periodontal ligament cell*[tiab] OR MLO-Y4[tiab] OR MLO Y4[tiab] OR MLO A5[tiab] OR MLO-A5[tiab]

Bone related

bone resorption[[mesh](#)] OR **Bone and Bones[[mesh](#)]** OR **Bone Development[[mesh](#)]** OR **osteoporosis[[mesh](#)]** OR **Osteopetrosis[[mesh](#)]** OR bone formation[tiab] OR Resorption[tiab] OR resorbing[tiab] OR Bone remodeling[tiab] OR bone remodelling[tiab] OR Bone re-modeling[tiab] OR bone re-modelling[tiab] OR (Mineral*[tiab] AND matrix[tiab] AND deposit*[tiab]) OR Resorpt*[tiab] OR Osteoporosis[tiab] OR osteoporotic[tiab] OR osteopetrosis[tiab] OR osteopetrotic[tiab] OR bone diseas*[tiab] OR osteolysis[tiab]

Osteoclast

osteoclasts[[mesh](#)] OR osteoclast*[tiab] OR pre-osteoclast*[tiab] OR preosteoclast*[tiab] OR resorbing cells[tiab] OR odontoclast*[tiab] OR cementoclast*[tiab]

Osteoclast precursors

monocytes[[mesh](#)] OR **Hematopoietic Stem Cells[[mesh](#)]** OR **Monocyte-Macrophage Precursor Cells[[mesh](#)]** OR monocy*[tiab] OR THP*[tiab] OR RAW264*[tiab] OR RAW 264*[tiab] OR RAW-264*[tiab] OR Mononuclear cell*[tiab] OR monoblast*[tiab] OR promonocyt* OR Mononuclear fraction[tiab] OR ((Hematopoietic[tiab] OR haematopoietic[tiab]) AND (stem[tiab] OR [stromal]))

Co-culture

coculture techniques[mesh] OR co-cult*[tiab] OR cocult*[tiab] OR coincubat*[tiab] OR co-incubat*[tiab] OR multi-cultur*[tiab] OR multicultur*[tiab] OR tri-cultur*[tiab] OR tricultur*[tiab] OR cultured together[tiab] OR cultivated together[tiab] OR Cell interaction*[tiab] OR Two cell types[tiab] OR (simultaneously[tiab] AND (seeded[tiab] OR cultured[tiab])) OR Bone model[tiab] OR Bone models[tiab] OR (Coupling[tiab] AND (bone OR formation OR resorption OR remodeling OR remodelling)) OR Resorption model[tiab] OR Model of resorption[tiab] OR Mixed culture[tiab] OR Synchronous cult*[tiab] OR Simultaneous cult*[tiab] OR binary cult*[tiab] OR dual culture[tiab] OR bi-cult*[tiab] OR colocalization[tiab] OR co-localization[tiab] OR colocalisation[tiab] OR co-localisation[tiab] OR heterocult*[tiab] OR heterotypic cult*[tiab] OR organoid[tiab] OR organotypic cult*[tiab] OR Trans-well[tiab] OR Transwell[tiab] OR Permeable barrier[tiab] OR Well insert[tiab] OR Well inserts[tiab] OR Well-insert[tiab] OR Well-inserts[tiab]